

Peak	Size [bp]	Conc. [pg/ μ l]	Molarity [pmol/l]
1	35	125.00	5,411.3
2	197	2.21	17.0
3	502	2,357.89	7,113.0
4	511	238.74	708.3
5	524	1,766.48	5,103.1
6	1,514	8.16	8.2
7	2,202	16.22	11.2
8	3,114	19.31	9.4
9	5,486	18.30	5.1
10	6,401	15.32	3.6
11	7,381	12.49	2.6
12	8,280	10.81	2.0
13	10,380	75.00	10.9